

Expression Analysis of Genes of Type IV Secretory System of H. Pylori in Different Gastrointestinal DiseasesFeeshan Ahmed¹, Vijay Kumar Ramnani², Aleem A Khan³¹PhD Scholar, Department of Microbiology, LN Medical College Bhopal Madhya Pradesh²Professor and Head, Department of Microbiology, LN Medical College Bhopal Madhya Pradesh³Head of Department, Central laboratory for stem cells and Translational medicine, Center for liver Research and Diagnostics, Deccan College of Medical Sciences, Kanchanbagh Hyderabad

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Abstract:

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) has been classified as a class I carcinogen which infects approximately half of the world's population with certain geographical variations. This has made *H. pylori* infection as a global public health issue. Differential disease outcome has further led more interest in understanding the molecular pathogenesis of *H. pylori*. Advancements in the proteomics, transcriptomics and accessibility to partial or complete *H. pylori* genome sequences helped in understanding the complex gene regulation networks of *H. pylori*. Yet, the precise molecular mechanism through which the *H. pylori* infection can cause a significant clinical result remains unknown. It was believed that a combination of factors like host genetic factors, environmental factors, and specific bacterial virulence genes are involved in *H. pylori* pathogenesis. Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to determine the molecular pathogenesis of *H. pylori* by examining the transcript expression of type 4 secretion system genes in a variety of patients with gastrointestinal disorders (GIDs), by extracting DNA/RNA from biopsies, and amplifying the relevant genes using PCR. Further, the type 4 secretion system gene expression patterns were correlated with different grade of gastric diseases, to elucidate the role of *H. pylori*'s molecular pathogenesis. The findings of the research revealed that GID patients had significantly higher type 4 secretion system gene expression. Specifically, of the 240 DNA samples examined, 240 (100%), 209 (87.1%), 225 (93.7%), and 234 (97.5%) of the subjects had *hrgA*, *cagA*, *cagE*, and *cagT*, respectively. A predictive biomarker for early gastric cancer diagnosis may be developed using the correlated expression analysis of transcripts from type 4 secretion system genes.

Keywords: *H. pylori*, Cag A, Gastric cancer, Gene expression, Predictive Biomarker.

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Introduction

The pathogenicity of *Helicobacter pylori* is associated mainly with *H. pylori* type IV secretion systems (T4SSs). These T4SSs represent remarkable molecular transporter machines with an extracellular pilus structure present in *H. pylori* which are commonly composed of multiple structural proteins spanning the inner and outer membranes. By definition, these T4SSs exhibit central functions as the secretion of effector proteins in mammalian host target cells. In recent years, numerous features on the molecular functionality of these T4SSs were disclosed. *H. pylori* encodes up to four T4SSs on its chromosome, namely the Cag T4SS present in the cag pathogenicity island (cagPAI), the ComB system, as well as the Tfs3 and Tfs4 T4SSs, some of which exhibit unique T4SS functions. In the *H. pylori*-associated diseases pathogenic mechanisms, several strain-specific virulence factors were reported, such as cag A (cytotoxin-associated gene

A), cag T, cag E, vac A (vacuolating cytotoxin A) and *hrg A*, genes. One of the main virulence factors is Cag A, which is associated with higher risk of gastric cancer and peptic ulcer. Cag A protein can interact with intercellular proteins and activate signalling pathways through both tyrosine phosphorylation-dependent or independent mechanisms. (Quigley, E. M. et al 1987, Chen S, et al 2001) The interindividual differences in risk of *H. pylori*-induced gastric diseases involve significant heterogeneity of both host genetics and *H. pylori* strain virulence factors. About 70% of *H. pylori* strains have been found with cag PAI gene. The cag A gene comprises 40 kb of chromosomal DNA with 32 open reading frames (ORFs), such as cag1 to cag 26, cag A to cag Z. The pathogenic mechanism of Cag A protein involves aberrant cellular signaling which may result in gastric cell malignancy (Fischer et al 2011, Hatakeyama et al 2005). Previously it was observed that the

expression of *cag A* gene varies among *H. pylori* strains that might be due to several host interactions which are opt for bacteria survival and its pathogenicity [Torres J et al 1998, Batista SA 2011]. Several in vivo studies have been reported the aberrant expression of virulent genes in development of gastric cancers (T. Franco et al 2005, Franco AT, et al 2008), however, there are no studies on correlation of virulent gene expression and host gastric cancer development from Indian population. The current study aimed to evaluate the *H. pylori* virulence gene *cag A* expression and correlate the expression pattern with gastric cancer development and other inflammatory responses.

In a study evidence indicates that the risk of gastric cancer or premalignant lesions is higher in persons infected with *cag A*-positive *H. pylori* strains than in persons infected with *cag A*-negative strains (Blaser MJ et al 1995, Plummer M, et al 2007.). The increased risk of gastric cancer observed with *cag A*-positive strains (which often contain the entire *cag PAI*) is attributed to the cellular effects of *Cag A* combined with an enhanced gastric mucosal inflammatory response (Suzuki N, et al 2012).

Cag A was described as the first bacterial oncogene but as with many other oncogenes in humans, the story became even more complex. The disease-associated factor *Cag A* is also associated with health, and its lack can lead to disease. Although *cag A*+ *H. pylori* strains were preferentially associated with both ulcers and gastric cancer, we and others found that these same strains had an inverse (protective) relationship with premalignant and malignant conditions of the esophagus, specifically Barrett esophagus and esophageal adenocarcinoma (Chow WH, et al 1998).

The present study was undertaken to know the association of *Cag PAI* -genes and different gastrointestinal diseases.

Methodology

Study Design

This study was carried out from 2019 to 2022 at Centre for liver research and diagnosis laboratories and Dept of Gastroenterology, Deccan college of Medical sciences and allied hospitals, Hyderabad, India. Study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee, Deccan College of Medical Sciences, and Hyderabad, India. A total of

515 subjects in the age range 18 to 60 years who had undergone upper gastrointestinal endoscopy were included in the study. An informed consent was taken from all patients and other demographic data which include questionnaire on their place of origin, profession, diet, smoking and alcohol habits had recorded. Clinical history regarding the duration and frequency of abdominal pain, heartburn, vomiting, nausea and previous history was also recorded. Subject less than 16 Years and on antimicrobial therapy and H2 receptor blockers, proton pump inhibitors, and NSAID prior to endoscopy were excluded from study.

Subjects infected with HIV, HCV and HBV, suffering with any other type of cancers (other than Gastric cancer) or any other co-morbid diseases and infected with active or latent TB were also excluded from the study.

The endoscopic findings of each patient were classified into 5 categories:

1. Gastric Adenocarcinoma,
2. Peptic Ulcer Disease,
3. Duodenal Ulcer,
4. GERD
5. Gastritis

DNA Isolation Gastric biopsy:

Gastric Biopsies of all 515 subjects was collected during the procedure of upper gastrointestinal endoscopy by using sterile forceps and appropriate measures were taken to ensure aseptic collection of the specimen. Biopsy was collected in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) for genomic DNA isolation.

DNA Isolation:

Genomic DNA was isolated from all samples as per the standard protocol by the Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide method. (Clayton et al 1998). All the extracted DNA samples were screened for 16 S rRNA PCR for the presence of *H.pylori*.

Screening of *H. pylori*

16S rRNA PCR

DNA was amplified using 16S rRNA PCR to determine the presence of *H. pylori*. The Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was carried out by using 16S rRNA primers and the DNA isolated from biopsy specimens of the subjects. The amplified product gives a 534 bp band upon agarose gel electrophoresis using a 1.5 % agarose gel at 120v, shown in Figure:

Table 1: Primers utilized to identify the *Helicobacter pylori*-specific 16S rRNA

Target gene	Primer sequence (5'→3')	Product size (bp)
16SrRNA of <i>H. pylori</i>	F- 5'- TAAGATCAGCCTATGCC - 3' R- 5'- TCCCACGCTTTAAGCGCAAT - 3'	534 bp

Figure 1: Gel imaging displaying the 16s rRNA gene's amplified result.

Here, Lane 1,2,4,5 and 6: Amplified 16s rRNA gene, product of size 534 bp,

Lane 8: PCR marker (New England Bio labs)

PCR Conditions:

The reaction conditions for the 16S rRNA gene amplification with both the primers were optimized and are as follows 950 C for 5 min (Initial denaturation step), 940 C for 30 sec 560 C for 30 sec, 40 cycles 720 C for 30sec, 720 C for 5 min (Final extension step).

Positive and negative controls are kept for the validation of the PCR performed. The negative control consists of the reaction mixture without the DNA template. The positive control contains the H. pylori DNA as the template.

Electrophoresis Conditions:

PCR products were visualized after electrophoresis at 120v on 1.5% agarose gel containing 1µl /ml ethidium bromide under UV light. The PCR product size was 534 bp.

Analysis of type 4 secretary genes H. pylori

Following type 4 secretary genes of H. pylori involved in Gastric pathogenesis.

- Cytotoxin-associated gene A (Cag A)
- Cytotoxin-associated gene E (Cag E)
- Cytotoxin-associated gene T (Cag T)
- (Hrg A)
- Vacuolating cytotoxin A (Vac A)

Primers and Target genes

Oligonucleotide primers selected to detect the cagE, cagA, cagT, hrgA and vacA genes of Helicobacter pylori

Table 2: oligonucleotide primers chosen for identifying the Helicobacter pylori genes cagE, cagA, cagT, hrgA, and vacA

Target gene	Primers pairs	Sequence (5'→3')	Amplicon size (bp)	Reference
cagE	cagE-F	GCGATTGTTATTGTGCTTGTAG	329	Ikenoue et al. (2001)
	cagE-R	GAAGTGGTTAAAAAATCAATGCCCC		
cagT	cagT-F	ATGAAAGTGAGAGCAAGTGT	842	S.K. Tiwari et al. (2007)
	cagT-R	TCACTTACCACTGAGCAAAC		
cagA	cagA-F	GATAACAGGCAAGCTTTTGA	499	S.K. Tiwari et al. (2007)
	cagA-R	CTGCAAAAGATTGTTTGGCA		
hrgA	hrgA-F	TCTCGTGAAAGAGAATTTCC	594	Ando et al. (2002)
	hrgA-R	TAAGTGTGGGTATATCAATC		
vacA	vacA-F	ATGGAAATACAACAAACACAC	259 (s1) / 286(s2)	Mukhopadhyay et al. (2000)
	vacA-R	CTGCTTGAATGCGCCAAC		

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

PCR was carried out on 240 H. pylori positive samples using Cag A, Cag E, Cag T, Hrg A and Vac A Oligonucleotide specific as mentioned above (table).

PCR Amplification: 19 ml of the reaction mixture containing 1X PCR buffer (50 mmol KCl, 10 mmol Tris-HCl [pH 8.3], 1.5% [v/v] Triton X-100), 1.5

mmol MgCl₂, 200 mmol concentrations of each dNTP, 10 pmol of each primer, and 1 U of Taq polymerase (Invitrogen Life Technologies, Karlsruhe, Germany) were combined with 1 mL of the template DNA. The PCR amplification process involved a 5-minute initial denaturation at 95°C, 40 cycles total, with one cycle consisting of 30 seconds at 94°C, 30 seconds at 52°C, and 1 minute at 72°C. The last cycle comprised a 10-minute

extension step to guarantee that the PCR products are fully extended. A thermocycler was used to perform the amplification. (USA: Watertown, MA; M J Research). On a 1.5% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide for visibility, the PCR products were examined. As a positive control, *H. pylori* DNA (type ATCC 26695) were utilized, whereas water was utilized as a negative control.

Results:

Molecular diagnosis results (16S rRNA PCR)

The patients with *H. pylori* infection were confirmed by *H. pylori* species specific 16srRNA gene amplification. Out of total 515 screened gastrointestinal tissue biopsies, 240 were found positive for *H. pylori*. Gastrointestinal disease based analysis showed, Out of 240 *H. pylori* 75 patients were found gastric adenocarcinoma, 40 and 45 patients were found peptic ulcer, duodenal ulcer respectively. Further 50 patients were found to suffer from gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and 30 were diagnosed to have Gastritis.

Table 3: Combined result of all 240 isolates for each of the five type *H. pylori* genes

No of subjects with different GI disorder n=240	Cag A	Cag E	Cag T	Hrg A	Vac A	
					S1 allele	S2 allele
Gastric adino carcinoma (n=75)	75(100%)	75(100%)	75(100%)	75(100%)	62(82.7%)	13(17.3%)
Peptic ulcer (n=40)	40(100%)	40(100%)	40(100%)	40(100%)	40(100%)	-
Duodenal ulcer (n=45)	36(80%)	35(77.7%)	39(86%)	45(100%)	30(66.7%)	15(33.3%)
GERD (n=50)	38(76%)	50(100%)	50(100%)	50(100%)	28(56%)	22(44%)
Gastritis (n=30)	20(66.6%)	25(83.3%)	30(100%)	30(100%)	19(63.3%)	11(36.7%)
Total n=240	209(87.1%)	225(93.7%)	234(97.5%)	240(100%)	179(74.5%)	61(25.5%)

Based on the 16S rRNA amplification, it was found that all 240 participants tested positive for *H. pylori*. The existence of an active *H. pylori* infection was confirmed by amplifying all of the DNA samples using 16S rRNA-specific oligonucleotide primers, which produced a product of 534 bp characteristic to *H. pylori*. Following a 16S rRNA positive test, each of the following

genes was examined individually: *cagA*, *cagE*, *cagT*, *vacA* signal region (*s1-s2*), and *hrgA*. Out of the 240 DNA samples that were analyzed, 240 (100%), 209 (87.1%), 225 (93.7%), and 234 (97.5%) of the participants had *hrgA*, *cagA*, *cagE*, and *cagT*, respectively. Of the *vacA*-positive subjects, *vacAs1* and *s2* have been identified in 179 (74.5%) and 61 (25.5%), respectively.

Figure 2: Type 4 secretory gene positive percentage in various gastrointestinal disorders

Figure 3: Cag A percentage positivity in various gastrointestinal diseases

Figure 4: Depicting the percentage of positive Cag E in various gastrointestinal diseases

Figure 5: Shows the percentage of positive Cag T in different gastrointestinal conditions

Figure 6: Hrg A positive percentage across a range of gastrointestinal disorders

Figure 7: Shows the percentage of Vac A s1/s2 positive in different gastrointestinal disorders

Discussion

The presence of *Helicobacter pylori* in the stomach tissue was confirmed by 16S rRNA amplification. In this study 16S rRNA PCR amplification is the "standard" for confirming the presence of an active *H. pylori* infection. 16S rRNA primers have been employed in multiple investigations that support increased sensitivities and specificities. (Ho S, et al. 1991, Weiss J, et al. 1994.).

In the course of our analysis, the biopsy specimens of all 515 patients revealed 240 positive results for 16S rRNA PCR amplification in 5 different categories of gastrointestinal diseases. The results of the 16S rRNA amplification show a 534 bp product size. The visibility of the desired band

with each primer set on an agarose gel, indicates that amplification with distinct primers spanning diverse areas of *cag* PAI produced a positive result. Based on the data of our study, the *hrgA* gene was the most often amplified virulence marker across all 240 (100%) samples, followed by *cagT* (97.5%), *cagE* (93.7%), and *cagA* (87.1%). S1 alleles were found in 74.5% and S2 alleles in 25.5% of the 240 samples that were included, and all of them tested positive for *vacA*. In our investigation peptic ulcer demonstrated 100% significant value to all 5 genes. A latest study indicates that strains obtained from ulcer patients had a notably greater frequency of all individual genes and intact *cagPAI* than strains obtained from patients without ulcers. (Markovska, R et al 2018). Compared to individuals with GERD

and Gastritis, patients with overt disease presentations such as gastric cancer, duodenal ulcer, and peptic ulcer had a higher prevalence of the s1 subtype of the *vacA* gene; these findings were determined to be statistically significant ($P < 0.01$).

The fact that the *hrgA* gene was 100% prevalent in all disease groups, regardless of clinical category, is another significant finding of this study. This study's result is significantly different from that of (Ando et al. 2002), who found that patients with stomach cancer had a greater prevalence of *hrgA* separated from them than did patients with cancer in Asia. Further investigation into the cause of this inconsistent outcome in a large sample of *H. pylori* from various geographic locations is necessary.

A recent study by Jenk et al. found that while the presence of the complete *cag* PAI is strongly linked to duodenal ulcers, the analysis of several *cag* PAI genes, such as *cagA*, *cagE*, and *cagT*, does not consistently predict the clinical outcome of *H. Pylori* infection. While *cagE* was not consistent with *cagT*, it was entirely consistent with *cagA* in the study conducted by Jenk et al. In a different investigation, *cagE* and *cagT* were found to have 96.6% consistency in the case of people with duodenal ulcers by Ikenoue et al.

On the other hand, our study, which included 40 patients with peptic ulcers and 45 patients with duodenal ulcers infected with *H. pylori*, demonstrated that, when compared to *cagA*, *cagE* and *cagT* were the most reliable markers to confirm the presence of *cag* PAI. This was because *cagE* was detected in 93.7% of the subjects and *cagT* in 97.5% of the total cases included in the study. According to Barrozo, R.M, et al. 2013, *CagT* is essential for translocation of the effector protein *CagA* into the epithelial cells. In contrast to previous studies (Ogura K, et al 2000.) that focused on the presence of *cagE* or *cagA* as likely virulence markers influencing the disease's fate, the current study therefore indicated for the first time that *cagT* could be the key gene controlling the disease's outcome.

It was found that nearly every sample of ulcer-affected participants had *cagT*, and a considerable proportion of patients in other groups also carried the *cagT* locus. Only one locus (*cagT*) is linked to the severe consequence of *H. pylori* infection, which is duodenal and peptic ulcers, despite a thorough investigation of the status of *cag* PAI and the features of what is known as a key pathogenicity factor, i.e., the *cagA* gene. Because the genes in the *cag* PAI have been passed down as a whole during evolutionary events that have occurred after their integration, it is well known that these genes encode proteins that are extremely similar in their function. Rather than being caused

by a single virulence factor, virulence is more likely the outcome of a confluence of factors, such as the presence of *cag* PAI together with those encoding cytotoxin production and adhesion expression. (Covacci A, et al 1997) However, no meaningful correlation could be found in the current investigation between the *cag* PAI isolation status and the study groups' enrollment. Rather, a significant determinant called *cagT* was discovered, which may contribute to the development of the disease's severe form. Our study showed that the genes involved in type 4 secretary system of *h. pylori* have higher positivity in our severe gastrointestinal diseases.

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